

SECTION OF HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE RELATIONS BETWEEN STATE AND RELIGION UNDER THE AZERBAIJAN DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC

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Abstract

The present article covers the work done to ensure freedom of religion and regulation of state-religious relations during the reign of Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (ADR). First, social and political processes during the ADR proclamation, as well as the measures taken by Russian Empire to overthrow the independent state are considered. The role of the Azerbaijani intelligentsia representatives in ensuring national unity is touched upon. The formation of various public and political organizations for this purpose, the transformation of most places of religious worship into a political arena for the people, the active role of religious figures in the creation of an independent state were noted. The article highlights the great work carried out by the ADR government towards the settlement of state-religious relations, the preparation by the national government of a number of legislative acts in various fields, as well as the opening of the new cultural and educational centers, despite the short time of the ADR government being in power.

Keywords: period, parliament, republic, religious figures, religious freedom, places of worship.

Introduction

The late 19th and early 20th centuries signified major transformations both globally and locally. The region experienced an acceleration of socio-economic processes, the beginnings of a bourgeois society, and the emergence of new political parties and organizations.

Meanwhile, the economic situation in Russia deteriorated, the political authority was increasingly undermined with strike movements spreading throughout the country. Considering this reality, the nation's leadership took firm political steps and enacted a series of actions to protect the rights and freedoms of its citizens. However, none of these decisions were enough to stop the negative processes, maintain political stability, and safeguard authority in the nation. It was already too late, and the processes had moved into an irreversible stage.

While Russia dominated the Caucasus, the situation in Azerbaijan was far more tense than that of its neighbors. Whereas neighboring countries had national schools, churches, national press, and various charitable organizations, all of this was forbidden for the Azerbaijani people. There was trust and care for the Christian church, but mosques in Azerbaijan endured oppression (1, p. 60).

On December 11, 1905, Emperor Nicholas II enacted a resolution to convene the State Duma, allowing Muslims of the Caucasus to participate in it. Capitalizing on this historical opportunity, the Azerbaijani intelligentsia actively engaged in political processes, sought to liberate the people from oppression, and organized efforts to achieve independence. Consequently, the press frequently featured articles encouraging the people to awaken and unite, focusing on the necessity of making the most of the historical opportunity. Those appeals were crucial in Azerbaijan's fight for independence in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, ultimately leading to the independence.

Research methodology. The article utilizes general scientific methods of analysis, synthesis, systematization, generalization, and correlation, alongside explanatory and critical historical, systemic, sociocultural, and comparative approaches.

1. The Fall of the Tsarist regime

The February bourgeois-democratic revolution of 1917 marked the end of three hundred years of tsarist rule. This event fostered the continued consolidation of liberation movements among the nations residing in Russia. Throughout the South Caucasus, including Azerbaijan, the national-democratic movement expanded significantly. This process saw active participation from members of the national bourgeoisie and intelligentsia. The resolutions to acknowledge the independence of Poland, Finland, Ukraine, and the Baltic nations, adopted following the October Revolution, greatly bolstered the national-democratic movement in other areas. The drive for national statehood started to cover more territories, and the quest for liberation from oppression, as well as the fight for freedom of speech, language, and religion, emerged as the primary goals of this movement.

Being concerned about the strengthening of the national liberation movement in Azerbaijan amid the broader surge of national movement, Russia aimed to deter Azerbaijanis from drawing closer to the Ottoman Empire by inciting the ethnic and religious conflicts, enforcing a policy of Russification, and trying to erase their Turkic heritage. Muslims in Russia, including Azerbaijanis, were not called up for military service, as the tsarist government was apprehensive that Muslim soldiers would refuse to battle the Ottoman Empire and could potentially use their arms against Russian colonizers. Due to their lack of trust in Azerbaijanis and other Muslims facing oppression during the war, the Russian authorities instituted strict control measures, declaring a state of emergency in Azerbaijan starting in

the summer of 1916. Throughout the war, Russia regarded Azerbaijan as a source of raw materials, a vital economic base, and a strategic military point for offensives against the Ottoman Empire, taking all measures to avert any unfavorable incidents (2, p. 66).

The Provisional Government, formed after the February Revolution of 1917, aimed to sustain the empire and perpetuate colonial practices. On March 17, 1917, it declared its readiness to comply with all international agreements made under the tsarist regime and the commitments taken on by Russia.

The Special Transcaucasian Committee (OZAKOM) was established to oversee the South Caucasus on March 9, 1917, made up of local members of the State Duma. The committee was chaired by Kharlamov V. A., a member of the Constitutional Democratic Party (the Cadets Party), and among its members were Cadet and later Musavatist Jafarov M. Y., Socialist and Federalist Abashidze K., as well as Cadets Papadjanian M. and Pereverzev P. Two days later, under the directive of Lvov G. E., Chairman of the Council of Ministers, Pereverzev was replaced by the Menshevik Chkhenkeli A., a member of the Social Democratic Party of Georgia.

As a result of the Bolshevik armed revolution in Petrograd on October 25, 1917, the Provisional Government was overthrown. At the Second Congress of Soviets in Smolny on October 25-26, the decrees "On Peace" and "On Land" were adopted, and the Soviet regime was established led by Lenin V. I.

On November 2, 1917, the Soviet government adopted the "Declaration of the Rights of the Peoples of Russia". This document outlined the main principles of the national policy of the Soviet government. The declaration covered the issues of equality among all peoples of the former Russian Empire, their right to self-determination, the repeal of all social, national, and religious privileges, and the development of national minorities and ethnic groups living in Russia.

The Soviet government, headed by Lenin V. I. and Stalin I. V., addressed an appeal "To All the Muslim Workers of Russia and the East" on November 20, 1917. The appeal highlights that the religious traditions and customs of Muslims, their national and cultural institutions, and their rights to live freely must be respected and protected (2, p. 69-70).

Consequently, amid the strengthening of the national identity of the Azerbaijani people and efforts to put an end to all manifestations of colonialism, the favorable conditions developed for the proclamation of the sovereign Azerbaijan Republic. The proclamation of independence represented the main goal of the local population, exhausted of the colonial subjugation by the tsarist government and wishing to establish their own national state (3, p. 3-4).

At the time, the practice of sending talented Azerbaijani youth to different educational establishments in the empire and around the world produced significant outcomes. Upon their return home after graduation, these young individuals contributed significantly in shaping and advancing the national-democratic movement. In their engagement with progressive ideas in Europe, they gradually recognized that achieving great objectives required them to reconnect with their historical

memory, understand their identity, and study the history and spiritual values of their nation.

Efforts were undertaken in this area: national schools were opened, educational programs were created, textbooks were written, and exemplary works from various foreign authors were translated into Azerbaijani. The key figures of the national intelligentsia of that era, such as Hasan bey Zardabi, Ali bey Huseynzade, Ahmad bey Aghayev, Nariman Narimanov, Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, Mahammad Hadi, Huseyn Javid, Uzeyir bey Hajibeyov, Mirza Alakbar Sabir, Abdulla Shaig, Alimardan bey Topchubashev, Firidun bey Kocharli, Mahammad Amin Rasulzade, etc., played a vital role in awakening the consciousness of the people and shaping the nation through their writings in the media. In this context, the thoughts of Hasan bey Zardabi and Mahammad Amin Rasulzade on patriotism and statehood, alongside Jalil Mammadguluzadeh's ideas about democracy and Azerbaijanism, had a remarkable influence.

2. Formation of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic

The processes of national revival, democratization, enlightenment, and charity, leading to the announcement of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, also saw active involvement from religious leaders. The initiatives for enlightenment and the promotion of science and education were led by respected figures who wielded considerable influence in society. After all, charitable efforts aimed at enlightenment and the promotion of science and knowledge would have inevitably failed without their support (4, p. 153).

During this time, the Taza Pir Mosque greatly influenced the formation of national-democratic forces in Northern Azerbaijan, which had been under Russian occupation for a prolonged period, in their efforts to turn Baku into a political center. The Azerbaijani intelligentsia decided to hold a congress of Caucasian Muslims to address the conflicts instigated by Tsarist Russia between the Sunnis and the Shias. The decision was joyfully accepted by the religious leaders of both madhabs, and in April 1917, a large gathering was held in the "Ismailiya" building (currently the building of the Presidium of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan). Delegates from all regions of Northern Azerbaijan, as well as from Dagestan, Basarkechar, and Borchali, were invited to the three-day congress. Following the gathering, attendees proceeded from Ismailiya to the Taza Pir Mosque, where hundreds of religious leaders held the Friday prayer in the presence of the mufti and shaykh al-Islam. Following this, the shaykh al-Islam and the mufti hugged and swore on the Quran to work towards overcoming the hostility incited by the Tsarist government to end the conflict between the Sunnis and the Shias.

At this time, a whole series of events took place in the region, including riots in Russia and the Ottoman Empire and their fall, the rise of Islamic unity in the context of Muslim resistance to colonialism, and the establishment of "Ittihadchilig" (which translates from Arabic as "unity" or "solidarity") grounded in moral and ethical values. This concept was introduced for the

first time as a theoretical ideology among the intelligentsia of Northern Azerbaijan. Later, a political organization called "Muslimism in Russia" was created based on these ideas.

It should be noted that "Ittifaq al-Muslimin" was among the first religious-political organizations to arise on the territory of the empire following the bourgeois revolution in Russia in 1905. During 1905-1906, three congresses of the organization took place in St. Petersburg and Nizhny Novgorod, led by Topchubashev A. M. The core mission of this organization was to achieve protection for the rights of Muslims living in Russia.

3. The Contribution of Azerbaijani Intelligentsia to the Establishment of the Democratic Republic.

At that time, the benefits of the concept of 'Ittihad-Islam' (Unity of Islam) were actively debated in Northern Azerbaijan by the public figures like Ahmad bey Aghayev, Ali bey Huseynzade, Akhund Yusif Talibzade, Mirza Abdurrahim Talibov, etc. Aghayev A. and Huseynzade A., reflecting the realities of Northern Azerbaijan in their perspectives, contributed fresh and original ideas to "Ittihad-Islam". Following this, Northern Azerbaijan saw the formation of political parties and organizations founded on the principles of "Ittihad-Islam". As a result, in the Russian Empire, the concept of Islamic unity and its various expressions were condemned as pan-Islamism, leading to a relentless struggle against them. Extensive rights were provided to the Orthodox population, while among Muslims, Christianity was enforced, and their rights were suppressed.

The Organizational Committee, formed in July 1917, included not just the religious leaders. Among the members of the committee were public figures like Mir Yagub Mir Mehdiyev, a graduate of the Petrograd Polytechnic Institute and publisher of the 'Irshad' newspaper Bashir Bey Ashurbeyov, the Candidate of economic sciences Mahmud Guliyev, the physician Karimaga Sultanov, Aga Zeynal Taghiyev, the grandson of Haji Zeynalabdin Taghiyev, and religious figures including Akhund Mullah Alakbar Abasguluzade and Akhund Mullah Alakbar.

Shortly thereafter, "Ittihad-Islam" united with a Muslim organization founded in Russia and started issuing a newspaper titled "Islam in Russia". Eventually, "Ittihad", edited by Jeyhun Hajibeyli, became the official newspaper of the party. At the first congress, which took place in April 1919, the party was renamed the "Caucasian Ittihad Party". During the second congress, held on January 25, 1920, numerous members of the Musavat Party and intelligentsia joined it; the concept of "Ittihad-Islam" was pivotal in rallying the Muslim nations against the discriminatory policies of the Russian Empire.

At that time, this ideology was especially popular across all provinces of the Russian Empire. The first all-Russian census of 1897 showed that Muslims (13.9 mln, or 11.9%) were the second most populous religious group after Orthodox Christians (87.1 mln, or 76%).

4. The concerns of Tsarist Russia about the ongoing processes

The Russian government was concerned about the potential unification of Muslims within its territory. Having assessed the threat, the government took a few actions to avert the unification of Muslims. A letter sent in 1910 by the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Russian Empire to the Tsar's Council of Ministers noted: "Lately, influenced by numerous internal and external political factors, there has been an increase in national-religious propaganda among the Tatar-Muslim populations of Crimea, the Volga region, the Caucasus, and the Trans-Ural area. Such propaganda, which adopted a specific orientation towards not only the religious and cultural independence of the Muslim community in Russia but also the Tatarization and Islamization of various peoples and 'strangers' of different faiths in the eastern borders of the state, is certainly a cause for concern for the government" (4, p. 155).

Considering this reality, the Tsarist government was simultaneously spreading Orthodoxy among the Muslim nations under its control and studying the Islamic world with the help of missionaries and official representatives, adopting the administrative strategies of colonial powers such as England and France, while preparing plans to resist the national-cultural renaissance of these peoples under the pretext of combating Islamic ideology. To accurately assess the nature of the political and cultural developments among Muslims, conferences and events were held involving the representatives of the appropriate institutions and organizations.

5. Proclamation of the Declaration of Independence

Despite numerous challenges, on May 28, 1918, the National Council of Azerbaijan proclaimed the formation of the first independent and democratic republic in the Muslim world. The declaration of Independence of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic reflected articles concerning national and religious matters. The declaration stated:

1. From this day onwards, the people of Azerbaijan are the bearers of sovereign rights. Azerbaijan is henceforth a rightful independent state that encompasses southern and eastern Transcaucasia.

2. The Democratic Republic is now set as a form of political organization of the independent Azerbaijan.

3. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic seeks to establish good neighbourly relations with all the members of the international community and, in particular, with the neighbouring nations and states.

4. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic guarantees, within its boundaries, the civil and political rights to all the citizens indiscriminately of ethnicities, religion, social status and sex.

5. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic provides an ample scope for development to all the peoples that populate its territory.

6. The National Council elected by popular vote and the Provisional Government accountable to the National Council shall remain the supreme authority of Azerbaijan as a whole until such time as the Constituent Assembly is convened (5, p. 43-44).

The Declaration of Independence showed that the Azerbaijani people were assuming an entirely new political-legal and moral-psychological status – as a nation-state, differing from their previous cultural and national status. On May 30, news of the proclamation of independence by Azerbaijan reached all major political centers globally via radio and telegraph. Therefore, the National Council of Azerbaijan carried out an important historical mission for the Azerbaijani people. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic was the first Turkic nation built on secular principles (6, p. 141).

The establishment of the first national democratic state in Azerbaijan occurred in highly challenging circumstances. Refusing to accept Azerbaijan's independence, both internal and external adversaries created disorder through tricks and manipulations, inciting conflicts and obstructing constructive efforts. There were also various groups with hostile intentions within the republic.

Following the founding of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, the Soviet Russia engaged in a policy of non-recognition and utilized all means to combat it. As of its founding, Soviet Russia followed the principle of "unified and undivided Russia". However, in the summer of 1918, Soviet Russia had very limited capacity to influence the political and military processes in the South Caucasus, and at that time, the Bolsheviks focused all their efforts on Baku, seeking to hold onto this city, being crucial for the Soviet government (2, p. 303).

6. The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic's care for religion

A government was established on June 17, 1918, and in order to revive national traditions and address the religious needs of the population, the Ministry of Spiritual Affairs and Public Enlightenment (MSAPE) was created, led by Yusifbeyli N. B (7, p. 308). The ministry quickly initiated active cooperation with religious authorities and institutions. The national and religious composition of Azerbaijan was reflected in the country's parliament: 80 seats were designated for Muslims, and 35 seats for Christians, with Armenians holding most of them. They had 21 representatives in the parliament (6, p. 205).

The government of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic managed to create a single spiritual administration for the Muslims of the Caucasus and promote cooperation between Shia and Sunni religious bodies. Prior to the declaration of independence, these religious authorities were based in Tbilisi. However, considering the difficult situation in the region, the leaders of both spiritual administrations – Shaykh al-Islam Mahammad Pishnamazzadeh and Mufti Mustafa Afandzade – made the decision to relocate to Azerbaijan. Following the decision of the MSAPE on August 10, 1918, they moved to Ganja and voluntarily united into a single organization on September 1, 1918. The MSAPE approved this decision on September 7, and after the liberation of Baku from the Bolsheviks in 1918, the spiritual administration was moved there.

At this time, the influence of religious leaders in the republic grew, a national army was swiftly established, and the role of "military mullah" was created

within the armed forces. The republic's leadership attached particular importance to this matter and maintained strict oversight over it. The work of military religious figures was monitored by the Ministry of Defense and the religious authority.

At that time, many religious locations served as centers for public discourse, and the religious leaders supported the national awakening. The Taza Pir Mosque and the Ismailiya building were among such centers. The adversary recognized the value of the Taza Pir Mosque for the unity of the Azerbaijani people. As a result, on March 31, the Dashnak-Bolshevik forces initiated the genocide of the Muslim population by setting fire to the Ismailiya building, a significant part of the architectural heritage that played a crucial role in the socio-political life and the awakening of national identity in the early 20th century, as well as to the editorial and printing office of the Kaspi newspaper, destroying 5,000 recently printed copies of the Quran.

7. Religious Leaders' Protest Against Genocide

Throughout the March events of 1918 and afterwards, the Taza Pir Mosque coordinated the funeral arrangements for tens of thousands of Muslims subjected to genocide and helped foster Muslim unity along with various preventive initiatives. Amidst the hardships that struck the Azerbaijani nation, numerous patriotic members of the intelligentsia visited the Taza Pir Mosque, calling on people to remain patient and steadfast.

It is important to note that among the religious figures of that period, Agha Alizade, the mullah of the Taza Pir Mosque, was notable for his dedication and patriotic fervor. The Baku Council's leadership required the mullah to issue a fatwa denouncing the actions of Ottoman soldiers who arrived to help liberate Azerbaijani lands from Bolshevik and Dashnak forces. The city's authorities even aimed to stress the confessional distinctions, portraying the arrival of Ottoman soldiers in Baku as a significant wrongdoing. Despite the threats, Mullah Agha Alizade stood firm and refused to comply with their demand.

In mid-September, Baku was liberated from Bolshevik forces by the Islamic Army of the Caucasus, commanded by its 29-year-old leader Nuri Pasha (Kilgilil). In response to the residents of Baku, Mullah Agha Alizade welcomed Nuri Pasha, the commander of the Islamic Army of the Caucasus, to the Taza Pir Mosque on September 16. Accompanied by Mullah Agha Alizade of the Taza Pir Mosque, Nuri Pasha stepped onto the minbar. He went up a mere three steps. Big black banners were set up on both sides of the minbar. Nuri Pasha delivered his speech calmly, holding onto one of them. The people of Baku observed the ceremony with admiration, and as Mullah Agha Alizade remarked: "Almighty Allah sent the Ottoman soldiers to aid their Muslim brothers, to save them from the infidels". This event underscored that the Taza Pir Mosque and its mullah Agha Alizade played leading roles in all political issues related to the nation's life (8, s. 27).

Tired of oppression and disorder, the Azerbaijani people looked for powers that could reestablish order

and peace in the nation. Many Azerbaijanis perceived this power in the Turkish people. Nuri Pasha's entrance into Ganja with 300 troops and the rapid reestablishment of order in the city bolstered the Azerbaijanis' admiration for the Turks even more (9, s. 204).

In October 1918, a gathering of leaders from both the Shias and the Sunnis took place at the initiative of Pishnamazzadeh. Since Mufti Huseyn Gayibzade died in 1917, during the disintegration of the Russian Empire, there was no new appointment of a mufti. Mustafa Afandizade, chosen at the administration meeting, served as the acting mufti. Mustafa Afandizade was closely associated with Pishnamazzadeh and greatly respected the wise, far-sighted, and caring shaykh al-Islam. On October 30, 1918, a letter with proposals No. 367, signed by the shaykh al-Islam, was forwarded to the government. The proposals were divided into 4 sections:

1. There is a need to create a spiritual authority named "Mashikhat-i Islamiyyah" within the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic and to provide it with complete independence, like the Mashikhat that exists in Tü-rkiye.

2. The proposal from September 7, numbered 311, specifies that one of the two chairmen of the Mashikhat should be titled shaykh al-Islam, and the other one should be called "mustashar" or advisor.

3. The shaykh al-Islam must be granted the right to attend sessions and be acknowledged as an official member of the Council of Ministers.

4. Funds should be allocated for staffing the spiritual personnel, to be placed directly under the authority of the Mashikhat. In order to resolve the mentioned and other related matters, an emergency meeting with our involvement should be convened.

The religious leadership, headed by Shaykh al-Islam M. Pishnamazzadeh, proposed this intricate idea and subsequently put it into action. As a result, they brought an end to the policies of Tsarist Russia that sought to incite animosity among the Muslims of the Caucasus by leveraging religious divisions.

This marked the culmination of Pishnamazzadeh's efforts in advancing our independent nation. Therefore, the religious leaders, not waiting for government instructions, took the initiative to unite and reestablish the Spiritual Administration of Muslims of the Caucasus called "Mashikhat", modeled after the one in the Ottoman Empire. On September 1, 1918, a collective decision was reached to merge both administrations into a single entity named "Mashikhat" (10, s. 186).

8. Relocation of the Mashikhat to Baku

Following the liberation of Baku on September 15, 1918, a decision was made to transfer the Mashikhat to Baku. On December 10, 1918, Mullah Mahammad Pishnamazzadeh stepped down from his roles as the chairman of the administration and shaykh al-Islam due to the health reasons. On December 12, by referral of Musa Bey Rafiyev, the Minister of Social Security and Religious Affairs of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, 47-year-old Agha Alizade, the akhund of the Taza Pir Mosque, was appointed as the chairman of the Spiritual Administration of Muslims of the Caucasus and

shaykh al-Islam. As a result, the autonomous dual Sunni and Shia spiritual structure that governed the religious matters of Muslims was dissolved, leading to the creation of a single administration for Muslims in the Caucasus. The shaykh al-Islam was appointed as the head of the administration, acting as the chairman of the Spiritual Administration of Muslims of the Caucasus, while the mufti became his assistant (3, s. 12).

On May 28, 1919, the first anniversary of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic was celebrated as a national holiday. During his speech Shaykh al-Islam Agha Alizade stated: "Freedom can only be protected and maintained by living independently. One can only speak about their views and beliefs and express their will in a free country. Both secondary and higher independent educational institutions will cultivate aware individuals who can acquire all the knowledge useful for the nation. The commandments of Almighty Allah can only be successfully implemented under state independence" (8, s. 56).

On September 15, 1919, Shaykh al-Islam Agha Alizade addressed a gathering at the Chemberekend Cemetery, where he paid tribute to the Ottoman and Azerbaijani soldiers who fell in the battle for the liberation of Baku. This ceremony was attended by the representatives from the state, government, and parliament of Azerbaijan. Shaykh al-Islam Agha Alizade prayed for Allah's mercy for the martyrs who died for the independence of Azerbaijan and blessed the soldiers going to the Karabakh front, wishing them success in defending their homeland. The national government commemorated March 31, 1919-1920, as the Day of Genocide of Azerbaijanis. Following the decree of Shaykh al-Islam Agha Alizade, mourning and commemorative events were held in every mosque in Azerbaijan on this day.

Conclusion

To conclude, it should be emphasized that before the occupation of Northern Azerbaijan by the 11th Red Army, the National Council of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, followed by the parliament and government, undertook a wide range of reforms in different areas of the economy and social life, playing a vital role in bolstering the independence of Azerbaijan during their brief existence. The decisions and initiatives focused on ensuring the citizens' rights placed a special emphasis on freedom of conscience.

The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic adopted crucial actions to safeguard national traditions, including fulfilling the religious needs of its citizens. Friday became a day off, and on religious holidays, representatives of all denominations were granted leave from their jobs. The government also enacted reforms within the religious sphere. According to the government's decision, religious figures and organizations received financial support from the budget, and religious taxes were channeled directly into the state treasury.

During this period, under the direction of Huseyn Arablinski, the Azerbaijan State Theatre was established in Baku, and the work of various societies, organizations, and unions aimed at promoting education and national culture saw considerable growth. Societies

including "Turk Ojaghy," "Nasiri-Maarif," and "Madani-Maarif" embarked on extensive endeavors.

Existing political parties in Azerbaijan substantially enhanced their efforts in agitation and propaganda. They provided lectures focusing on the history, literature, and culture of Azerbaijan, as well as published books.

Concurrently, the ideology of Azerbaijanism manifested itself in the establishment of a national state and its intentional activities across all spheres of government and societal life, dominating the minds of a considerable part of the population.

Although the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic survived for less than two years, it succeeded in many areas, including the restoration of Azerbaijan's state structure, the revival of the country's independence, and the awakening of our people's national self-awareness.

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